

Ion-exchange Capacity of the Bottom Sediments of the River Ganga

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The cation-exchange capacities of the river Ganga sediments have been found to be appreciable from the estimates of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} suggesting appreciable mobilisation of clay minerals and nutrient load necessary to sustain soil fertility. However the analysis of the results in terms of enrichment factors shows that there is considerable depletion of Na, K, Ca and Mg due to chemical erosion and these are transported by the river water making the water rich in these ions.

Sediments can be regarded as sinks for materials transported from the land. Many naturally occurring substances such as trace metals and nutrients, may be mobilised as a result of natural processes and also by man's activities and may thus become enriched in sediments of river beds, particularly in coastal and estuarine regions.

One of the most useful, but often neglected management-oriented types of investigations involve sediments. Sediments are reservoir for many pollutants including metals. Monitoring sediment quality can give a long-term, cost-effective picture of pollution climate of water-bodies. The studies on sediments may be of great help in determining various aspects of water pollution, pollutional loads of the river, the influence of man's activities on the exchange capacities of the sediments. Martin and Meybeck¹ carried out extensive works on the correlation of elemental mass-balance of material carried by major world rivers on the basis of estimate of average composition of river particulate matter (RPM) of the major rivers of the world. Geographic variations of major elements (40 elements) in RPM are linked to weathering types and the balance between weathering rates and river transport. The enrichment and depletion of elements can be determined from the proper analysis of RPM. A knowledge of RPM is of considerable importance in giving greater insight into crustal weathering processes on a global scale and in determining the elemental fluxes between land and ocean. This also enables one to compare the river-borne material with the oceanic suspended matter and deposited sediments.

The studies on the ion-exchange capacities of the sediments are of importance in ascertaining the nutrient load of the sediments. The ability of a soil to exchange ions is called the ion-exchange capacity expressed as milliequivalents per 100 g of soil (e.g. 1 meq of Na^+ = 23 mg Na^+). Cation-exchange capacity (CEC) has been used to define the sensitivity of soils to acid precipitation. Clay minerals and organic matter in soils contribute to their CEC.

Usually, the cation-exchange capability of the soil is limited. But the cation-exchange capabilities of the Ganga sediments can be regarded to be appreciable as observed from the estimates of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} suggesting the presence of fine clay particles in the sediments and hence their value from the viewpoint of augmenting soil fertility.

These considerations led us to study the ion-exchange capacities of the bottom sediments and the river Ganga at different depths and along the banks of the river. The study may give us some idea regarding enrichment or depletion of exchangeable ions in the sediment of the river Ganga.

Results and Discussion

The data (Table 1) show that the sediment is rich in potassium content compared to Na content. However, considerable depletion of K and Na are observed in sediments. We compare the average values of the ions in soils² ($K_{(\text{soil})}$ = 14000 mg/kg and $\text{Na}_{(\text{soil})}$ = 5000 mg/kg). In borehole-B, the K and Na contents decrease with depth but no such correlation can be made for K and Na contents in borehole-C though Na contents are usually lower and decrease with depth. However, K and Na contents decrease as we move from the sea.

Similar conclusions can be derived for Ca (concentration of Ca and Mg in soil are respectively 15000 and 5000 mg/kg). Ca^{2+} content decreases with depth in borehole-C but the relative concentrations in borehole-C are higher. The trend is similar for Mg^{2+} . However, concentrations of Ca^{2+} in bottom sediments (upper layers) are usually greater than those in borehole-B or -C. The Mg concentrations are usually higher in borehole-B or -C and remain more or less constant in bottom sediments.

The relative depletion of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} calculated from concentration factor F defined by $[\text{X}]_{\text{sediment}}/[\text{X}]_{\text{soil}}$ or enrichment factor EF defined by

$$\text{E.F.} = \frac{[\text{X}]_{\text{sediment}}/[\text{Al}]_{\text{sediment}}}{[\text{X}]_{\text{fr.}}/[\text{Al}]_{\text{fr.}}}$$

TABLE 1—SOIL PARAMETERS : EXCHANGABLE K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}

Sampling station no*	Depth, Position**	Approximate distance from the sea (km)	Exchangable cations (mol kg ⁻¹)			
			10 ³ K ⁺	10 ³ Na	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
B-1	1.00 m	100	9.7	10.0	0.34	0.30
B-10	15–15.6 m		8.4	6.1	0.31	0.23
B-14	20.4–21.0 m		7.7	6.1	0.29	0.13
B-15	22–22.5 m		7.7	6.1	0.25	0.21
B-21	30.75 m		6.4	3.6	0.27	0.27
C-5	9.45 m		8.1	6.1	0.42	0.21
C-7	13.05 m		6.4	1.3	0.47	0.13
C-10	16.8–17.4 m		8.7	5.2	0.32	0.20
C-14	22.05 m		6.4	1.7	0.30	0.13
C-20	30.1–30.7 m		7.4	3.5	0.30	0.13
3(R)	On the bank	195	5.9	14.4	0.57	0.13
18(R)	On the bank	140	6.7	1.3	0.38	0.17
48(R)	On the bank	105	6.7	12.6	0.41	0.19
17(L)	On the bank	140	5.1	17.8	0.39	0.16
23(L)	On the bank	135	7.9	9.2	0.35	0.18
25(L)	On the bank	130	4.4	13.0	0.07	0.19
49(L)	On the bank	100	6.1	1.3	0.42	0.21
49(L)	3m ^a	100	5.6	1.3	0.47	0.13
50(L)	On the bank	97	6.9	1.3	0.29	0.09
50(L)	7m ^b	97	6.4	39.6	0.38	0.13
51(L)	On the bank	27	23.3	25.7	0.45	0.13
52(L)	On the bank	10	14.3	19.6	0.31	0.11
52(L)	8m ^c	10	25.3	11.7	0.42	0.13
52(L)	9m ^a	10	10.0	10.9	—	—
53(L)	On the bank	97	8.4	12.2	0.55	0.13
54(L)	On the bank	47	4.9	13.0	0.52	0.18
55(L)	On the bank	Patna	4.9	10.4	0.47	0.14
58(L)	On the bank		5.9			

*Bank of the river : R≡right, L≡left. **Away from the bank : ^a500ft, ^b200ft, ^c100ft.

where, $[X]_{\text{sediment}}$ is the average content or concentration of the element $[X]$ in the sediment. $[X]_{\text{fr}}$, the average content or concentration of the element $[X]$ in the surficial fresh rock, $[Al]_{\text{fr}}$, the average Al content in surficial fresh rock, and $[Al]_{\text{sediment}}$ the average content or concentration of Al in the sediment determined previously in our laboratory³.

Al is chosen as standard as it is poorly soluble and as yet not affected by pollution. It is assumed that Al has reached a steady state at the continental surface, i.e. not at present being accumulated by the soil layer and is derived only from land erosion. The enrichment factor can be estimated assuming

$$\frac{[X]_{\text{fr}}}{[Al]_{\text{fr}}} \approx \frac{[X]_{\text{soil}}}{[Al]_{\text{soil}}}$$

The E.F. values show that there is considerable depletion of Na, K, Ca and Mg due to chemical erosion. The compounds are highly soluble and transported easily by the river. The results corroborate the observation that the Ganga water is rich in Na, K, Ca and Mg ions and the water is relatively hard.

The results are also in accord with the observations of Martin and Meybeck¹ that Na, K, Ca and Mg are strongly depleted as a result of chemical erosion which globally represents 25% of the total river load.

Experimental

The samples of soils at various depths were collected from the works carried out by Dadina Pvt.

Ltd. in connection with the subsoil investigation work for the proposed intake Jetty of Calcutta Metropolitan Development Authority at Kamarhati. The samples were taken from foundation point of view.

Ten samples at different depths (upto 30 m) of the Ganga were collected in polythene bags 30 m from two boreholes-B (about 30 m away from the bank, water depth 8.50 m from river bed levels) and borehole-C (about 60 m away from the bank, water depth 10 m from river bed levels). Bottom deposits were collected at several locations at different depths along the breadth of the river during slack periods. The grab samples at various depths were also collected in polythene bags. Samples were also collected from Patna at different places. The samples were collected in polythene bags.

All the samples were soaked with filter paper to remove water and air dried at room temperature. The samples were grouped in two categories : (i) samples collected at various depths at Kamarhati (collected during the years 1985–86) and (ii) samples collected from the bottom sediments near the banks stretching from Kalyani to Katchuberia (near the sea) during the years 1986–87 and samples collected from Patna. In few cases, samples were collected crosswise at different depths of the river.

The standard methods of extraction and estimation of exchangeable cations were followed⁴. The air-dried soil (10 g) was stirred well with $CH_3CO_2ONH_4$ solution (250 ml) for 2 h. The suspension

was filtered and the filtrate was stored in polythene bottle. The Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} content in the filtrates were estimated in the usual way using EDTA, while Na^+ and K^+ contents were determined by using a Systronics FPM 125 MK-1 flame photometer.

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